

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B306
Date: 15 July 2007
Take Off: 13:04:13
Landing: 17:01:17
Flight Time: 3h57m04s

Campaign: COPS

Operating Area: Baden-Baden, Germany

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Phil Brown	Met Office
5	Mission Scientist 2	Alan Blyth	UFAM
6	Flight Manager	Steve Devereau	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
8	Core Chemistry / CCM2	Stuart Heath	FAAM
9	VACC 1	Barbara Brookes	Leeds University
10	VACC 2	Angela Dean	Leeds University
11	CPI 1	James Dorsey	University of Manchester
12	CPI 2	Hazel Jones	University of Manchester
13	CVI	Jeff Brown	Met Office
14	Nephelometers	Andy Wilson	Met Office
15	AMS	Will Morgan	University of Manchester
16			
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B306 Track 15-JUL-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B306
 Date: 15th July 2007
 Project: COPS
 Location: Baden-Baden

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
122558		event	0.36 kft	160	INU to Nav
125102		Start-Up	0.36 kft	160	
125547		event	0.36 kft	160	start taxi
130413		T/O	0.34 kft	211	
130628		event	3.5 kft	213	Nevzorov zero
130915		event	6.0 kft	048	JW zero
131344	131648	Profile 1	6.0 - 2.5 kft	260	
131655	132921	Run 1.1	2.4 - 2.5 kft	208	
131922		event	2.5 kft	207	Heimann cal
133035	133418	Profile 2	2.5 - 5.5 kft	098	
133554	134624	Run 2.1	5.5 kft	016	
133636		event	5.5 kft	013	Nevzorov, JW zero
134718	135043	Profile 3	5.5 - 2.5 kft	260	
135108	140243	Run 3.1	2.5 kft	207	
135221		event	2.5 kft	200	Nevzorov, JW zero
140356	140641	Profile 4	2.5 - 5.5 kft	096	
140815	142009	Run 4.1	5.5 kft	014	
142211	142937	Profile 5	5.5 - 14.0 kft	182	
143226		event	14.0 kft	085	Nevzorov, JW zero
143258	143444	Run 5.1	14.0 kft	084	
143452	143557	Profile 6	14.0 - 15.0 kft	117	
143626	143750	Run 6.1	15.1 - 15.0 kft	306	
144059		event	15.0 kft	204	Nevzorov, JW zero
144247	144630	Run 6.2	15.0 kft	046	
144717	144837	Profile 7	15.0 - 16.5 kft	200	
145011	145120	Run 7.1	16.5 kft	224	
145437	145805	Run 7.2	16.5 - 16.6 kft	005	
145601		event	16.5 kft	044	Nevzorov, JW zero
145848		event	16.5 kft	157	icing on FFC during cloud penetration
145913	150043	Profile 8	16.5 - 17.5 kft	204	
150700	150951	Run 8.1	17.5 - 17.4 kft	037	
151104	151159	Profile 9	17.4 - 18.5 kft	221	
151802	152106	Run 9.1	18.5 kft	048	
152251	152315	Run 10.1	19.4 - 19.5 kft	323	
152517	153117	Run 10.2	19.5 kft	234	
153021		event	19.5 kft	051	Nevzorov, JW zero
153129	153341	Run 10.3	19.5 kft	048	
153507	154108	Profile 10	19.5 - 14.1 kft	229	
154506	154720	Run 15.1	14.0 - 13.9 kft	056	
154903	154943	Profile 11	14.1 - 14.5 kft	232	
155103		event	14.5 kft	232	Nevzorov, JW zero
155347	155529	Run 16.1	14.5 kft	051	
160139	160351	Run 16.2	14.5 kft	055	
161025	161358	Run 16.3	14.5 kft	061	
161852	162120	Run 16.4	14.5 kft	032	
161928		event	14.5 kft	029	Nevzorov, JW zero
163110	163549	Run 16.5	14.5 kft	045	
163809	164528	Profile 12	14.5 - 7.5 kft	217	
164712	164947	Profile 12	7.5 - 5.5 kft	036	
165133	165516	Run 17.1	5.5 kft	284	
170117		Land	0.42 kft	213	
170624		Shutdown	0.42 kft	164	

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE
IN KNOTS FOR ISOBARS AT 4 MB INTERVALS
POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION

B306 Track 15-JUL-07

PROJECT BRIEF: COPS - Convective and Orographically-induced Precipitation Study.

Scientific Aims: The goal of UK-COPS is to determine the properties of the aerosols that will likely be ingested into the convective clouds that form over the Black Forest mountains and to understand the formation and growth of ice and precipitation in these clouds . We wish to examine:

- the properties of the representative aerosol particles in the clear air that are transported into the convective clouds
- the concentration and size of cloud droplets just above cloud base
- the formation of the first ice due to primary nucleation on ice nuclei (IN)
- the development of ice via secondary processes such as the Hallett-Mossop process, in which new ice particles are generated during the riming growth of ice particles
- other secondary ice production processes, such as evaporative break-up;
- the production of supercooled raindrops and their role in the glaciation process
- the dependence of these processes on the dynamics of the cloud
- the production of precipitation

There will either be 2 flights per day: one in clear air to measure the properties of the aerosols and one later in the convective clouds; or the two parts will be flown in a single flight. Measurements will be made in cumulus clouds when their tops are about 0°C through to when the tops have grown to about -20°C.

Weather conditions:

Developing showers over the Black Forest mountains, Germany, within Box A and probably B.

Safety: Regions that paint RED on the aircraft weather radar should be avoided. No flight into clouds known to be producing lightning. There may be coordination with the DO-128 in Boxes A and B. The French and German Falcons may also be operating in the area.

Key instruments and their operation:

Basic meteorology

- Rosemount temperatures, GE hygrometer
- GPS, INU, turbulence probe. When in supercooled liquid water, Flight Manager or PIs should monitor turbulence probe and calibrated differential pressures for signs of icing (cessation of variability on signal).

Cloud Physics/Aerosol

- FFSSP, 2DC, 2DP, PCASP, CDP, CIP, SID-1 and SID-2. Normal monitoring to ensure correct operation. Operator should note particular features of interest eg. high concentrations, appearance of pristine ice crystal habits, appearance of large drops ($d > 100 \mu\text{m}$) in 2D imagery when above freezing level.
- CPI as above
- J-W LWC and Nevzorov LWC/TWC. Where straight/level and in clear air, these should be zeroed/calibrated and a note made in the Flight Managers log.
- TWC - profile ascents/descents should avoid cloud if possible
- AMS -
- CVI - below cloud base, normal operation is in aerosol mode; above cloud base, normal operation is in CVI mode
- VACC - in straight and level clear-air, 10 min runs; during cloud work and profiles, single temperature.

Sortie Brief: COPS – Convective and Orographically-induced Precipitation Study
Flight Number: B306
Date: 15 July 2007
Mission Scientists: Phil Brown and Alan Blyth
TO Time: 14:45 local

Sortie Aims: To measure properties of aerosols in the clear air and the development of convective clouds.

Sortie Location: Clear air in Rhine Valley and in convective clouds over Black Forest mountains. Leg over supersites.

Sortie Summary:

1. Characterise properties of aerosols in clear air at low levels.
2. Penetrate cumulus clouds preferably near the top of the cloud in the updraught. All cloud penetrations should be with *wings level*. Two principal options are:
 - A. stationary cloud or system of clouds;
 - B. several cumulus clouds either in area (low wind) or passing through the area.
3. Characterise properties of aerosols in detrainment layers around cloud.
4. Overfly supersites M, H and R.

Sortie Detail:

1. Out-of-Cloud: All changes in altitude at standard rates (1000 ft/min).
2 x Rhine Valley aerosol legs (70 mins)

2. Cloud work:

Note an important feature is to ascend with tops. This requires a non-standard ascent as fast as possible. Relay cloud top info to the DO-128.

Option A: Isolated developing clouds – ascend with the clouds near their top. All penetrations at constant altitude.

A.1 Proceed to about 0°C or top of cloud.

A.2 Adjust altitude to about 1000 ft below cloud top and penetrate cloud. The penetration should be made at a constant azimuth and altitude if possible. It is important to penetrate the growing turret in the updraught region. A few seconds after clearing cloud, turn and ascend for return to same region of cloud as quickly as possible using procedure turn.

A.3 Repeat A.2, ascending with the top (if appropriate) at the end of each penetration out of cloud, until FL200 or FL240, or cloud becomes too developed.

A.4 Repeat A.1 - A.3 for a new developing cumulus, go to **Option B**, or exit box.

Option B: Many developing cumulus clouds – sample clouds at constant altitude.

B.1 Proceed to 0°C

B.2 Commence 10 min runs (turning where appropriate) in along shear direction. Adjust track to randomly sample the updraught regions of growing turrets.

B.3 Ascend to -5°C (i.e. approximately 3500 ft) and repeat above for 10 min.

B.5 Repeat for -10°C, -15°C and -20°C if possible.

3. Detrainment layers

Proceed to level where cloud is being detrained from cloud and either make penetrations or circle around the cloud.

4. Leg over supersites Murg Valley (M), Hornisgrinde (H) and Achern (R) at about 5500 ft if in clear air. (15 min)

B306

15/07/2007

Mission Scientist Debrief:

Phil Brown

1. Flight patterns

Take off and climb to 6000ft initially. Descend to 2500ft over Baden Airpark (FKB) for southbound leg. Initial profile shows a small inversion at exactly this level, with significantly moister air below. See variations in dew point and aerosol variables along the leg due to fluctuations in inversion height.

Climb to 5500ft on eastbound leg, then northbound at this level. Again, see fluctuations in aerosol connected to "blue" convective updrafts. Cloud formation appears to be roughly in a line from S to N (along the low level wind direction) and towards the east side of the box A/B with first convective cells forming to the S of the boundary.

Further pair of 2500ft / 5500ft legs which pick up much the same structure as before. N end of 5500ft leg appears to have dew point 10 deg warmer (10C cf 0) than S end, consistent with stronger cloud formation in this area. Most recent climb to 5500ft was apparently a degree or so warmer than others.

Climb initially to FL140 (estimated freezing level), with cloudbase at ~9500ft. Profile was along and under many of the cumulus bases – spot the gliders – although mostly avoiding actual cloud penetration. Sequence of cloud penetrations at FL140, 150, 165, 175, 185, 195 roughly following ascending cloud tops in this mass of cumulus. Precipitation particles presumed low concentration as radar echoes only reach into green. LWC peaks up to ~ 1.2 gm-3. There has been a significantly deeper cell growing up well above FL195, probably to ~ FL300, just outside the area. Obviously significant ice development in it but no obvious precip to the ground.

Following collapse of the first patch of clouds, descent to FL140 again. Profile appears to reproduce the previous climb. Then sequence of cloud penetrations at FL140 and 145 (T~ -2.5C). These have some updrafts within and LWC peaking above 1 gm-3, but are not now deepening much above this level. Clouds now obviously dissipating.

Profile descent back to FL055, passing over supersite M along the way. Multi-layered structure in aerosol variables, associated with minor stable layers during the descent. Will be interesting to look at all tracers.

Final 5500ft leg starting just over supersite M and passing over H and R to provide some in-situ validation material before descent back to FKB.

2. Summary of weather conditions

Ridge axis to the east of COPS area, with westerly upper flow. Surface winds from the south in the Rhine valley. Moist surface layer below 925 hPa, but clouds form in the layer above this with significantly less moisture, hence high cloudbase 9500ft. Additional heating over the mountains is presumably responsible for cloud triggering. Initial cloud formation was only ~1hr prior to take off and largely confined to the Black Forest area. Some ocnl cells triggered over the S. Vosges early on but this had largely dissipated during the flight period.

Clear air runs identified significant structure in both the horizontal and vertical in T, Td, aerosols and other tracers.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

P
Pitt
BROWN

Flight No **B** 306
FAAM © 2004

Date 15/07/07

Page 1 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1303					L/O FCRB
/					line of Co forming over B forest
/					Tops may just be reaching F100 expected freezing level ~ F140.
1307		6000			level.
131344		"			Start P1 for 2500
/					Cloud formation is some way west of the H summit
131655		2500			Start R1. over FCRB
131842					Surface moist layer, even at 925 hPa they do it above, seems to be the pic above 925 hPa that is feeding cloud base -
1324					approaching lat, cloud formation is S of the box A/B boundary.
1329		2500			aerosol conc. fluctuations along Run 1
132922					Run 1.1 end.
133035		"			Start P2.
/					Dipping in and out of the surface layer
133418		5500			End P2
133554		"			Start R2.1
/					Updraft picking up extra aerosol.
133755		"			2 pic of clouds to R of present track, + top of aerosol layer.
1344					Deeper clouds in N part of B.
/		"			some turbulence here.
					wind 5/190deg
134624		"			End 2.1 point C

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.306**
FAAM © 2004

Date **15/07/07**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
135043		2500			End P3 ^{pit} over valley of moister than over S end of B. For.
135708		"	207		Start 3.1 FKB.
1358				See	Td variation from 4 to 14C as we cross the surface layer boundary.
—		"			End 3.1
140356		"			Start P4 for 5500.
—					cloud line currently seems to have gap in the middle.
140815		5500			Start 4.1
1411ish					Photo of clouds in S part of box.
141515					photo at crossed layer at cloud base.
—					P4 warmer than stars?
					Big change of dew point also
		5500			Start P5 for 10000
					clouds are currently on the A/B boundary
		9500			cloud base, clouds are just above.
—					wind 270 deg.
					profile is under & through cloud line.
		14000			End P5
143200					in cloud.
		15000			-5 peak LWC ~ 0.7
					T-3.6 out of cloud.
144445		"		higher LWC	in cloud. tops ~ 2000
—					Fine email now at S side of box
		16500			-65

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.306** Date **15/07/07** Name Page **3** of **4**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1451		16500			just thro small cell.
145650		"			in cloud, detached anvil behind.
				N. low	cone of precip. no echoes.
		17500			NTWC low again, -8
150920					in cloud.
		18500			major cloud with anvil just out of S edge box. -10
					Camera 2 min slow prior 2 this.
		"		main	top ~ 10000 above
		19500			quick pass through.
		"			R 10.2 towards H.
					Clouds collapsed so profile descent back to 140
154035					Downward profile consisted with spread.
154635		14000			in cloud. 2 cells. ^{lwc 0.7} same as before.
		14500			-2.5
155500		"			0.45 lwc top 500 above.
160250		"			-2.5 in. lwc a bit higher this pass.
1611		"		16.3	in cloud. growing cell on this side.
					Note classic thermal structure off to RHS on entry to last cloud. poss 7ms ⁻¹ updraft
162037		14500			in cloud, still updraft.
163510		"			updraft passed over top of clouds.
					Can see stable layer out to R.
		"			Start profile.
164136		10500			in profile over M.
		8400			at box boundary.

layer structure in CNC counts

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B306 **T/O:** 13:03:00
Date of flight: 15/07/07 **Land:** 17:10:00

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt	NO	hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		
9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO	yes	NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful. X = A
a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D	-1.0 sec	Start = 130300 End = 171000 Time data processed to = 160258 2dproc files present *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat
10) FLOODS> WAVE	yes	Use PVWAVE for this section
i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit		Error message about HDDR file should be ignored. Records = 31
11) FLOODS> MODIFY	yes	
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default		MFDB
12) CHECKS:		
Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i>		No correlation at all

PCASP Processing

Flight number: B306
Date of flight: 15/07/07

T/O: 13:03:00
Land: 17:10:00

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Yes	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. 1.8ccs⁻¹</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Min size = 1 Vol flow rate = 1.0 130300 171000
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit	yes	Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>	yes	MFDC
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	yes	

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.306**.....

 Date **15/7/07**.....

 Operator's name: **Wilson**.....

 Page **1** of **2**.....

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
124500								preflight OK.
131655	1.1	2500ft ASL	12.2	30	24	↗	+6.4	Warming up, set water to +30 Preheater on off
1322				32	53		+30	Humidifier out RH 85%. Set water to +38 + flow to 14
132350			14	33	63	↗	+32	Hum out RH 91%. Set water to +40c
132630			13.8	22	76	↗	+40	Set to +43
133035	P2	2500ft → 11500		23	77	→	+43	Set water to +5c.
133418	P2 P2	11500	12.4	18	49	↘	29	end P2 @ 5000ft
133754	2.1	5000ft	12.8	15	36	↗	23	Set ramp up to +43c RH outside 18%
134500	"	"	10.6	33	74	→	+45	Preheater off off
134624		"	"	33	75	↘	45	end Run, set to +5c
134718	P3							Start P3 to 2500ft.
135043		2500ft		37	53		27	end P3
135108	P3.1	"	11.7	36	53	↗	27	start run & set water to +40c.
135522	"	"	9.0	24	60	↗	40	Set to +45 + drop flow to 10
140230	"	"	10	32	77	↘	+45	end Run, set water to +75c
140356	P4		"	"	"	↘	35	Start P4 to 5500ft.
140641	P4	5500ft	10	15	53	↘	26	end P4.
140815	P4.1	"	10	16.5	48.4	↗	22	start run and set water to +45c. inlet RH 14%
141700	"	"	8.6	17.4	76.3	-	45	max possible RH achieved.
142000			8.7	29.5	79.5	-	45	end P4.1. ramping down.

CVI Log B306

7/15/07 1:12:45 PM profile descent
7/15/07 1:15:43 PM start of run 1.1
7/15/07 1:28:15 PM end of run 1.1
7/15/07 1:29:33 PM profile climb
7/15/07 1:34:40 PM start of run 2.1
7/15/07 1:45:13 PM end of run 2.1
7/15/07 1:46:12 PM profile descent
7/15/07 1:50:02 PM start of run 3.1
7/15/07 2:01:22 PM end of run 3.1
7/15/07 2:02:49 PM profile climb
7/15/07 2:07:08 PM start of run 4.1
7/15/07 2:19:01 PM end of run 4.1
7/15/07 2:21:03 PM profile climb
7/15/07 2:35:30 PM in cvi mode for cloud penetratrion
7/15/07 2:35:46 PM run 6.1
7/15/07 2:41:41 PM run 6.2
7/15/07 2:49:03 PM run 7.1
7/15/07 2:54:01 PM run 7.2
7/15/07 3:05:36 PM run 8.1
7/15/07 3:17:22 PM run 9.1
7/15/07 3:21:43 PM run 10.1
7/15/07 3:24:14 PM run 10.2
7/15/07 3:30:37 PM run 10.3
7/15/07 3:43:45 PM run 11.1
7/15/07 3:52:40 PM run 12.1
7/15/07 3:53:14 PM run 16.1
7/15/07 4:01:25 PM run 16.2
7/15/07 4:09:15 PM run 16.3
7/15/07 4:17:45 PM run 16.4
7/15/07 4:30:38 PM run 16.5

Flight:

B306

KEY

- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK
- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevezorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

Report Created 20/08/2007
17:26:17

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:
- DLUs:**
- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:
- Aerosol**
- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3025 (AMS):
- INC:
- VACC:
- CPC 3010A (CVI):

01/08/2007 12:08:02

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B306

Date: 15/07/2007

Instruments

SID2 failed at mid-levels

AMS – no HORACE connection, but laptop connected using same cable ok. Suspect AMS PC set-up.

AMS problem cleared: comms cable plugged into wrong connector on AMS rack

Aircraft

None

Satcom-H Calls

Dornier crew

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 15/7/07

Flight No: B306

Pre-Flighter: BW

No.	✓ or x	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	H-Satcom No Response
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	WFC suspect
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up	Not fitted
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hubs x 4	Checked ON	
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	& CB on Port Fwd SSP
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	
27	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	No zero
28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	Set up	
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	CPI sect
Proceed to External Checks				
External Checks overleaf				

Pre-Flighter's Log

<u>No.</u>	<u>√ or x</u>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
<u>External Checks</u>				
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	<u>No photo</u>
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	<input type="checkbox"/>	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	<input type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	All other covers	Removed	
40	<input type="checkbox"/>	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
41	<input type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	<input type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				Signed
43	<input type="checkbox"/>	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		<u>NO ACCESS.</u>
44	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	ICEX applied		
45	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		<u>a) Nil b) 1-2 drops - c) 1/4 full or more</u>
46	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B306:

Log	Reason
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
VACC	VACC operator does not create a log sheet
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM
CPI	CPI operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0		Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Rearward Facing Cameras

3 x Forward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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New plot, same times

Flight B306 14:21:41

Heading 181 deg Speed 227 knots Height 5.4kft Press 827mb

Lat 48°42.0'N Long 8°30.0'E Wind 1 ms-1/ 242 deg

Temp 19.33C Dewpoint 11.0C

From 14:10:26 to now

	Current values		
	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	51699	secs
+++++	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	19.34	deg C
—	DEW POINT	11	deg C
			<input checked="" type="radio"/> All
			<input type="radio"/>
			<input type="radio"/>

Flight B306 14:05:14

Heading 91 deg Speed 214 knots Height 3.8kft Press 878mb

Lat 48°0.0'N Long 7°48.0'E Wind 6 ms-1/ 233 deg

Temp 24.57C Dewpoint 2.34C

From 13:54:49 to now

Current values			
DEW POINT	2.35	deg C	<input checked="" type="radio"/> All
CNC COUNTS	2680	p cm-3	<input type="radio"/>

Flight B306 13:18:24

Heading 204 deg Speed 233 knots Height 2.4kft Press 925mb

Lat 48°36.0'N Long 8°0.0'E Wind 3 ms-1/ 268 deg

Temp 25.23C Dewpoint 11.76C

From 13:00:24 to now

Current values		
STATIC PRESSURE	925.7	mb
DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	25.23	deg C
DEW POINT	11.77	deg C

Flight B306 15:41:09

Heading 212 deg Speed 240 knots Height 14.0kft Press 594mb

Lat 48°30.0'N Long 8°6.0'E Wind 11 ms-1/ 223 deg

Temp -1.44C Dewpoint -24.94C

From 13:00:24 to now

	Current values		
	STATIC PRESSURE	594.47	mb
++++	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	-1.44	deg C
++++	DEW POINT	-24.95	deg C

Flight B306 16:45:54

Heading 172 deg Speed 230 knots Height 7.5kft Press 766mb

Lat 48°12.0'N Long 8°6.0'E Wind 7 ms-1/ 157 deg

Temp 14.53C Dewpoint 0.95C

From 13:00:24 to now

	Current values		
	STATIC PRESSURE	766.65	mb
++++	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	14.53	deg C
++++	DEW POINT	0.95	deg C